

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Authoring the Pathway Organ Crosswalk Tables

Procedures for authoring the blood-vasculature-organ crosswalk, lymph-vasculature-organ-crosswalk, and peripheral-nervous-system-crosswalk tables

Authors: Griffin Weber¹, Katherine Gustillo²

Approved by: Katy Börner² (6/11/2024)

¹ Department of Biomedical Informatics, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA 02115, USA

² Department of Intelligent Systems Engineering, Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA.

Introduction

The procedures outlined in this document describe how to create and extend the pathway organ crosswalk tables, which list the relationships between three “pathway” based anatomical structures (i.e., [blood vasculature](#), [lymph vasculature](#), and [peripheral nervous system \[PNS\]](#)) and “nested partonomy” based organs (e.g., lung, kidney, spleen, etc.). These relationships include the anatomical structures within organs that blood vessels supply or drain, that lymphatic structures drain, or nerves innervate. These tables are an essential part of the Human Reference Atlas’s goal to build a Vasculature Common Coordinate Framework (VCCF), which uses vascular pathways (and PNS pathways) to describe the location of cells throughout the body. Note that these pathway organ crosswalk tables are different than the pathway crosswalk table, which describes relationships between pairs of blood vessels, lymphatic structures, and nerves (see the VCCF Section Overview for more details). The primary audiences for this SOP are the authors and reviewers of the three pathway-organ crosswalk tables.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Reviewer** is a domain expert in an organ, in blood vasculature, in lymph vasculature, or PNS, who reviews relevant portions of the tables and suggests corrections.

The **Table Author** is responsible for managing the content of the crosswalk table.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Reviewer (blood vasculature)	Sanjay Jain M. Todd Valerius	sanjayjain@wustl.edu mtvalerius@bwh.harvard.edu

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

	Gloria Pryhuber Martha Campbell-Thompson	gloria_pryhuber@urmc.rochester.edu thompmc@pathology.ufl.edu
Reviewer (lymph vasculature)	Robin Wang Valeria Bustos Griffin Weber Ellen Quardokus	robin8@stanford.edu vbhvale@hotmail.com weber@hms.harvard.edu ellenmq@iu.edu
Reviewer (PNS)	Griffin Weber	weber@hms.harvard.edu
Table Author (blood vasculature)	Katherine Gustilo Griffin Weber	katherine.gustilo@cuanschutz.edu weber@hms.harvard.edu
Table Author (lymph vasculature)	Dhruv Singhal Maxim Itkin Avinash Boppana	dsinghal@bidmc.harvard.edu maxim.itkin2@pennteam.upenn.edu asboppana@gmail.com
Table Author (PNS)	Katherine S Gustilo Ilias Ziogas Fahim Imam	katherine.gustilo@cuanschutz.edu ziogasiliass@gmail.com fahim.imam@queensu.ca

Procedures

Each of the three pathway-organ crosswalk tables use the same structure, though the names of the first two columns of the tables are different in each table to indicate blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, and peripheral nervous system (PNS). The tables can be found here: [blood vasculature](#), [lymph vasculature](#), and [peripheral nervous system \[PNS\]](#).

Table Authors and Reviewers are encouraged to construct and review an organ crosswalk diagram, using the relevant [SOP](#), before modifying the pathway-organ crosswalk tables.

Table Metadata: First 10 Rows

Similar to other Human Reference Atlas (HRA) tables, the first 10 rows of the pathway-organ tables are reserved for metadata. Row 1 contains the name of the table (e.g., “Blood Vasculature Organ Crosswalk”). Row 2 is intentionally left blank. Rows 3-10 include information about the authors, reviewers, general reference publications, the DOI of the table, and the date and version of the table. For details about rows 3-10, see the SOP on [Authoring ASCT+B Tables](#).

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Table Columns

Each row in the tables contains a single pathway-relationship-organ structure combination. A pathway can have a relationship with more than one organ structure and more than one pathway can have a relationship with the same organ structure.

See below for a list of columns and their descriptions.

Table 2. Column descriptions for Pathway Organ Crosswalk Tables

Column	Description
(Pathway)	The name of the blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, or PNS structure. In the blood vasculature table, this column is named "Vessel". In the lymph vasculature table, this column is named "LymphStructure". In the PNS table, this column is named "Nerve". This pathway should be listed in either the blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, or PNS ASCT+B table.
(PathwayID)	The ID (Uberon preferred, alternatively FMA) of the blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, or PNS structure. In the blood vasculature table, this column is named "VesselID". In the lymph vasculature table, this column is named "LymphStructureID". In the PNS table, this column is named "NerveID". The IDs should match the IDs of anatomical structures listed in the blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, or PNS ASCT+B table.
Relationship	The relationship between the Pathway and BodySubPart (organ anatomical structure). In the blood vasculature table, the relationship "directly_supplies_drains" is typically used for capillaries and the specific body sub-part that it supplies or drains. Larger blood vessels use the relationships "supplies" and "drains". Branches from these vessels extend to the body sub-part, but the vessels themselves do not directly supply or drain it. Other blood vessel organ relationships include "connected_to", "overlaps", "part_of", and "surrounded_by". In the lymph vasculature table, the relationship "drains" is used. In the PNS table, the relationship "innervates" is used.
BodySubPart	The anatomical structure related to the pathway. If possible, this should be an existing structure listed in a "partonomy" based organ ASCT+B table.
BodySubPartID	The ID (Uberon preferred, alternatively FMA) of the BodySubPart. This ID should match the anatomical structure in the organ ASCT+B table.
BodySubPartSequence	Along the length of a pathway, it might have relationships with multiple BodySubParts. The BodySubPartSequence is an integer that places these relationships in order. Use "999" as a default value to indicate

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

	that the sequence order has not yet been recorded.
BodyPart	The organ of the BodySubPart. If possible, this should be the Level 1 Anatomical Structure of a “partonomy” based organ ASCT+B table. In other words, it should indicate the ASCT+B table where the BodySubPart can be found.
BodyPartID	The ID (Uberon preferred, alternatively FMA) of the BodyPart. This ID should match the Level 1 Anatomical Structure ID in the organ ASCT+B table.
FTU	If this relationship is part of a Functional Tissue Unit (FTU), indicate the name of that FTU.
FTULabel	If this relationship is part of a Functional Tissue Unit (FTU), indicate the label of that FTU from an ontology (Uberon preferred, alternatively FMA).
FTUID	If this relationship is part of a Functional Tissue Unit (FTU), indicate the ID of that FTU from an ontology (Uberon preferred, alternatively FMA).
Angiosome	If this relationship is part of an Angiosome (a region of muscle, skin, or bone supplied by a primary artery), indicate the name of that Angiosome.
AngiosomeID	If this relationship is part of an Angiosome (a region of muscle, skin, or bone supplied by a primary artery), indicate the ID of that Angiosome.

Review process

- Confirm that the format of the table follows this SOP.
- Confirm that the Pathway IDs appear in a pathway ASCT+B table and the BodyPartIDs and BodySubPartIDs appear in a partonomy organ ASCT+B table.
- Confirm that the relationships are correct. If available, use a pathway-crosswalk diagram to confirm.
- Notify the Table Authors of any potential problems found.

References and Resources

Boppana A, Lee S, Malhotra R, Halushka M, Gustilo KS, Quardokus EM, Herr BW 2nd, Börner K, Weber GM. Anatomical structures, cell types, and biomarkers of the healthy human blood vasculature. *Sci Data*. 2023 Jul 19;10(1):452. doi: 10.1038/s41597-023-02018-0. PMID: 37468503; PMCID: PMC10356915.

Börner K, Teichmann SA, Quardokus EM, Gee JC, Browne K, Osumi-Sutherland D, Herr BW 2nd, Bueckle A, Paul H, Haniffa M, Jardine L, Bernard A, Ding SL, Miller JA, Lin S,

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Halushka MK, Boppana A, Longacre TA, Hickey J, Lin Y, Valerius MT, He Y, Pryhuber G, Sun X, Jorgensen M, Radtke AJ, Wasserfall C, Ginty F, Ho J, Sunshine J, Beuschel RT, Brusko M, Lee S, Malhotra R, Jain S, Weber G. Anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers of the Human Reference Atlas. *Nat Cell Biol.* 2021 Nov;23(11):1117-1128. doi: 10.1038/s41556-021-00788-6. Epub 2021 Nov 8. PMID: 34750582; PMCID: PMC10079270.

Weber GM, Ju Y, Börner K. Considerations for Using the Vasculature as a Coordinate System to Map All the Cells in the Human Body. *Front Cardiovasc Med.* 2020 Mar 13;7:29. doi: 10.3389/fcvm.2020.00029. PMID: 32232057; PMCID: PMC7082726.

Glossary

Angiosome: A region of muscle, skin, or bone supplied by a primary artery.

Anatomical structures: Parts of the body in defined locations and regions, including the surface, internal organs and tissues. These structures may be described by gross or microscopic morphology and include functional tissue units and highly organized cellular ecosystems (such as alveoli in the lungs).

ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid or metabolic markers).

Digital Object Identifier (DOI): A persistent interoperable identifier.

Functional Tissue Unit (FTU): The smallest tissue organization that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The HRA is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The HRA provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

Acknowledgments

The Human Reference Atlas (HRA) is under active development by the Indiana University Mapping Component as part of the HuBMAP HIVE, SenNet CODCC, KPMP, and GUDMAP efforts with expert input by the HRA Editorial Board and in close collaboration with experts from more than 18 other consortia. Data was provided by HuBMAP and other Tissue Mapping Centers. This research has been supported by the NIH Common Fund through the Office of Strategic Coordination/Office of the NIH Director under awards OT2OD033756 and

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

OT2OD026671, by the Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet) Consortium through the Consortium Organization and Data Coordinating Center (CODCC) under award number U24CA268108, and by the NIDDK under awards U24DK135157 and U01DK133090. The work has also been supported by the Kidney Precision Medicine Project grant U2CDK114886, and the NIH National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), Department of Health and Human Services under BCBB Support Services Contract HHSN316201300006W/HHSN27200002. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health.